

A revolutionary deep learning approach to the forecasting of cryptocurrency financial time series

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Abstract

Recently, “Stock Exchange” forecasting is considered as one of the most challenging tasks within the realm of time series prediction (Wang, et al., 2012). Specifically, cryptocurrency time series are usually known to be very complex, non-stationary and very noisy. This chaotic nature of crypto-coins makes very hard the adoption of classic time series models such as “Auto-Regressive Integrated Moving Average” (ARIMA) since they require strict assumptions regarding the distributions and stationarity of time series. On the other hand, “Deep Learning” (DL) is gaining even more attention in time series prediction since an « priori » analysis is usually not necessary (Bao, et al., 2017). The automatic feature extraction capabilities of deep neural networks do not demand prior knowledge of the time series structure and are quite reliable concerning the non-stationary time series. Furthermore, in recent years, more and more Deep Learning models have been employed to “Sentiment Analysis” (SA) thanks to their automatic high-dimensional feature extraction capability even from non-structured symbolic data such as generic texts (i.e. tweet). These breakthroughs are also due to the latest pre-processing discovers like Word Embeddings (Mikolov, 2013). Many studies prove that financial Sentiment Analysis is arising as an important research area of financial technology (FinTech). Indeed, the experimental results show how the “mood” extracted from various financial resources has significant effects on investments (Day & Lee, 2016) . “Sentiment” stands for one person’s subjective public standpoint about a specific topic.

Sentiment is typically expressed, on the web by users, under the unstructured form of an opinion, review, news, disapproval, etc. Sentiments have the power to affect opinions of product vendors, politicians and readers in general, namely the public opinion (Qurat, et al., 2017). In this work we propose a novel stack of cutting-edge Deep Learning models aimed to generate outperforming prediction accuracy and profitability in cryptocurrency forecasting. Namely, we leverage a new Deep Learning time-series model called WSAEs-LSTM by efficiently combining Wavelet-Transforms (WT) for data denoising; Stacked Autoencoders (SAE) for high-level feature extraction and LSTM (Long Short Term Memory) for modelling cryptocurrency prices historical data. On the other side, a Recurrent Convolutional Neural Network model (RCNN) achieving the “state-of-art” accuracy in sentiment classification, has been implemented (Lai, et al., 2015). RCNNs are bi-directional window-based LSTMs which have been trained on a corpus of 1.6 million tweets divided into positives and negatives, with a pre-trained embedding layer on the top. Our RCNN implementation achieves

85% of accuracy on this training set. Extracting keywords from the model's max-pooling layer, we can create a corpus of domain-specific keywords useful for a "topic summarization" or for following stages such as neural machine translation, etc. Therefore, RCNN learns what is a positive or negative sentiment and we have applied this discriminative capability to diverse sources of texts such as news, Reddit or tweets. Textual sources are preliminarily filtered according to crypto-coins or a general financial-oriented focus. Using RCNN we produce a sentiment time-series for each textual sequence which is eventually inserted as input to WSAEs-LSTM. The high accuracy of RCNNs and WSAEs-LSTM enables us to reach supreme levels of crypto-coin predictions by measuring RMSE (and MAPE) between real values of "close" and "volume" attribute and the predicted ones, as far as the -test set is exclusively concerned. The historical data entered into WSAEs-LSTM (other than the Sentiment time-series) are "high", "low", "open", "close", "volume", "weighted average" attributes of 63 different cryptocurrencies. A future direction to improve our system might be the adoption of Monte Carlo Tree Search (MCTS) and Deep Reinforcement Learning (Silver, et al., 2017) to run simulations for the "Wallet Management". The extraction of keywords from the RCNN model can lead to a word-centred machine translation (Bahdanau, 2014) using a sequence-to-sequence model with attention and beam-search. Hence, we can translate our textual information (tweets, news, reddit, etc) into another language (different from English) yielding a Universal Sentiment Analysis fostering the treatment of news in many different languages. Another our critical purpose is to interface this stack of models to a sequence-to-sequence model to develop a chat-bot able to expose all the financial sentiment information, keywords, summarizations and prediction to the users into the shape of natural language.

Keywords:

1. Keywords

cryptocurrency, forecasting, time-series, sentiment, analysis, multilingual, deep, learning, recurrent, convolutional, neural, machine, translation, wsae-lstm

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Author biography

Matteo Testi I am a Data Scientist with hands on Cloudera and Deep Learning.

Since my thesis dissertation in Data Science at the University of Dundee focus on deep learning and Health, I have been working on Cloudera ecosystem and as a Deep Learning engineer.

I am currently working in a Company Consulting, Sferanet srl, with a special focus on Cloudera Architecture/Implementation. I am the head of Data Engineer&Deep Learning Engineer (four people) to develop proof of concept for the client and develop new service/application for to grow up a business in my company. I'm also responsible for R&D where I manage a budget for develop projects in Deep Learning area. I got a different kind of experience:

- Cloudera Installation for a PoC

- I am working on Cloudera implementation and upgrade new release.

- I wrote the notice of research "Por life2020", and I have coordinated the project proposal. This work is born from my thesis as an extension of my work. The main subjects of this project were Deep Learning and Health.

- I coordinated and develop with my team a Sentiment Analysis program in Italian languages.

- I am working as a coordinator in a different project for Deep Learning with a focus on resolving health problems.

For a long time, I have been developing in R, Python and during my last work, I got to experience on developing using Cloudera's Ecosystem (Hive, Hadoop, Impala, Pig, Scala, Spark, Mahout, Sqoop, Flume, Kafka).

I believe to be a very creative person, always full of interesting ideas for the research and industry. I successfully directed the various team at my job.

I attended in Kaggle Competition "Data Science Bowl 2017" with my team. We got awarded a bronze star.

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My main research topics are: Cloudera's Ecosystem, Deep Learning, Neuroscience, Health

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